

Engagement Is Not Enough: A Mixed-Methods Study of Feasibility, Leadership, and Volunteer Retention in the UK Third Sector

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Volunteer retention remains a persistent challenge in the UK third sector. Despite high reported engagement and positive volunteer experiences, many organisations continue to experience turnover and episodic participation, calling into question assumptions that engagement alone is sufficient to sustain long-term involvement.

Aim: This study examines whether organisational factors commonly assumed to drive volunteer retention operate through engagement, or whether retention intention is more strongly shaped by organisational feasibility and role sustainability.

Methods: An explanatory sequential mixed-methods design was applied, combining survey data from 276 UK third-sector volunteers with qualitative open-text responses. Quantitative correlations examined relationships between leadership, organisational culture, recognition, engagement, training and development, and retention intention, while qualitative analysis interpreted these patterns.

Results: Leadership, organisational culture, and recognition were strongly associated with volunteer engagement but only weakly associated with retention intention. Training and development demonstrated the strongest association with retention intention, despite minimal association with engagement, indicating a distinct feasibility-based pathway.

Conclusion: The findings suggest that engagement is a necessary but insufficient condition for volunteer retention. Retention is better understood as a conditional process shaped by organisational feasibility and role sustainability, rather than as the overall outcome of motivational enhancement alone.

KEYWORDS

Volunteer retention; Volunteer engagement; Organisational feasibility; Leadership; Training and development; Third-sector, Charity

Introduction

Volunteer retention remains a persistent challenge across the UK third sector, with turnover and episodic participation disrupting continuity and increasing operational strain on charities and volunteer-led organisations (Hustinx and Lammertyn, 2003; Studer and von Schnurbein, 2013; Warburton et al., 2018). This persistence has remained evident even where volunteers report broadly positive experiences, strong identification with organisational purpose, and relational satisfaction (Eisner et al., 2009; Wilson, 2012). As a result, the longstanding assumption that increasing engagement will reliably translate into long-term participation has come under increasing theoretical strain (Vecina et al., 2012; Harp, Scherer and Allen, 2017).

Much of the established literature positions retention as a downstream outcome of motivational states such as engagement, satisfaction, and commitment, drawing heavily on organisational behaviour frameworks developed within paid employment settings (Kahn, 1990; Cropanzano and Mitchell, 2005). Leadership quality, organisational culture, and recognition are commonly defined as organisational levers through which engagement and commitment can be strengthened, therefore lowering exit (Bass and Riggio, 2006; Denison, 1990; Eisenberger et al., 1986). These perspectives offer valuable insight into how volunteering feels and how organisational relationships are experienced, but their retention implications are less straightforward in non-contractual contexts where exit costs are low and participation is frequently episodic or time-bounded, for example, the volunteer sector (Cunningham, 2008; Hustinx and Lammertyn, 2003; Macduff, 2005).

This article argues that persistent retention challenges are not primarily the result of ineffective engagement strategies but of a conceptual misalignment in how retention itself has been theorised. Retention has typically been considered a problem of motivational downfall, whereas volunteering is better understood as a conditional process where ongoing participation depends on organisational feasibility (for example, clarity, structure, preparedness, and role sustainability) and is bounded by lifecycle constraints and changing personal circumstances (Haski-Leventhal and Bargal, 2008; Hustinx, Handy and Cnaan, 2010; Wilson, 2012).

Drawing on an explanatory sequential mixed-methods study of volunteers in the UK's third sector (N = 276), this article empirically differentiates engagement from retention intention and examines how organisational factors function across these outcomes (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). Three hypotheses structure the analysis. Hypothesis 1 tests whether leadership behaviours and organisational culture are positively associated with

both engagement and retention intention (Bass and Riggio, 2006; Schein, 2010). Hypothesis 2 tests whether talent management and recognition predict engagement and retention intention, reflecting assumptions drawn from social exchange perspectives and perceived organisational support (Blau, 1964; Cropanzano and Mitchell, 2005; Eisenberger et al., 1986). Hypothesis 3 tests whether training and development are positively associated with retention intention and whether this relationship is stronger than the engagement–retention link commonly assumed in the literature (Rehnborg et al., 2005; Harp, Scherer and Allen, 2017).

The findings demonstrate a consistent pattern. Leadership and organisational culture are strongly associated with engagement but only weakly associated with retention intention, indicating that these factors shape experience quality more than participation duration. Recognition is widely valued and necessary but does not meaningfully differentiate retention outcomes, consistent with the idea that some relational practices may function as baseline expectations rather than retention mechanisms. In contrast, training and development show the strongest association with retention intention, despite a weak association with engagement, suggesting a feasibility avenue through confidence, preparedness, time availability and role sustainability.

The central contribution of this article is a feasibility-based reframing of volunteer retention. Engagement is positioned as a necessary but insufficient condition for sustained participation, while feasibility and role sustainability emerge as critical enablers. In doing so, the study clarifies why high engagement does not reliably translate into long-term retention and identifies feasibility as a missing construct in engagement-centric models of volunteer motivation and commitment.

2. Literature Positioning: Engagement–Retention Assumption

Volunteer retention research has slowly expanded, with emphasis on motivation, engagement, satisfaction, and commitment as explanatory mechanisms for continued participation (Clary et al., 1998; Hustinx, Handy and Cnaan, 2010). A significant proportion of this literature implicitly treats retention as a subsequent outcome of engagement, assuming that positive experiences, relational quality, and perceived organisational support will naturally translate into sustained participation (Kahn, 1990; Vecina et al., 2012).

This engagement-centric assumption has shaped how leadership, organisational culture, recognition, and support practices are theorised and implemented within volunteer research and practice environments (Bass and Riggio, 2006; Denison and

Mishra, 1995; Eisenberger et al., 1986). However, empirical findings increasingly suggest that engagement alone offers an incomplete explanation of retention, with high engagement frequently coexisting alongside volunteer exit and episodic participation (Studer and von Schnurbein, 2013; Warburton et al., 2018).

The limitation of this assumption lies in its insufficient attention to feasibility and limited evidence base within the sector, given the majority of retention practices are based on corporate or public sector environments. Volunteering is non-contractual, often driven by emotional connections, and continued participation is frequently shaped by capacity, role fit, time availability, health, and changing life circumstances, rather than by dissatisfaction or disengagement (Hustinx and Lammertyn, 2003; Macduff, 2005; Wilson, 2012). Yet feasibility remains under-theorised within dominant retention models, with organisational practices such as training, role clarity, and ongoing support typically framed as engagement enhancers rather than as retention conditions in their own right (Rehnberg et al., 2005).

This study addresses this gap by repositioning feasibility as a central explanatory concept. Rather than treating retention as the accumulation of motivation, it examines whether organisational conditions that enable sustained participation over time, are more strongly linked with retention intention than engagement-related factors alone. This reframing provides the problem context for the theoretical analysis that follows.

Volunteer retention research has expanded substantially, with sustained emphasis on motivation, engagement, satisfaction, and commitment as explanatory mechanisms for continued participation (Clary et al., 1998; Hustinx, Handy and Cnaan, 2010). A significant portion of this work is shaped by traditional models developed in employment and commercial contexts, including Transformational Leadership Theory, Organisational Culture Theory, and Social Exchange Theory (Bass, 1985; Denison, 1990; Blau, 1964). These frameworks have advanced some understanding of how volunteers interpret leadership, find meaning or purpose, and develop relational connections to organisations (Bass and Riggio, 2006; Schein, 2010; Eisenberger et al., 1986).

A key issue, however, is that retention is frequently operationalised or implied as an extension of engagement and satisfaction. Engagement is commonly characterised as a psychological condition characterised by enthusiasm, involvement, and meaningfulness, resulting in a direct precursor of commitment and reduced turnover (Kahn, 1990). Leadership and culture are consequently framed as central levers for retention because they influence engagement and perceived organisational support (Bass and Riggio, 2006; Denison and Mishra, 1995; Eisenberger et al., 1986).

This engagement-centric retention logic has limitations. First, studies report inconsistent and often modest associations between engagement-type concepts and sustained participation, with high engagement coexisting alongside substantial exit and episodic involvement (Studer and von Schnurbein, 2013; Warburton et al., 2018). Second, the structural conditions of volunteering materially alter a person's retention decision. Volunteering is discretionary and non-contractual, meaning continued participation is less bound by economic dependency and institutional obligation than paid employment and more sensitive to a volunteer's capacity, role suitability, time pressures, health, and family circumstances (Cunningham, 2008; Hustinx and Lammertyn, 2003; Wilson, 2012).

This points to a conceptual gap: dominant retention models under-theorise feasibility. While volunteer management literature acknowledges the importance of induction, structure, support, and development (Rehnberg et al., 2005), these are often framed as ways to increase engagement rather than as retention determinants in their own right. Yet sociological work on volunteering repeatedly highlights that participation is episodic and limited by lifecycle, and exit may reflect normal transitions rather than organisational failure (Hustinx and Lammertyn, 2003; Macduff, 2005; Haski-Leventhal and Bargal, 2008).

Consequently, the present study responds by empirically distinguishing engagement from retention intention and examining whether organisational factors operate through different pathways. Rather than treating retention as motivational growth, it tests whether organisational conditions that support role sustainability (e.g., training, development, and operational preparedness) are more closely aligned with retention intention than relational and cultural levers alone.

3. Methodology

Research Design

This study used an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design (QUAN → QUAL), analysing quantitative survey data first and then using qualitative open-text data to explain and contextualise observed statistical patterns (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018).

Sample and Data Collection

Quantitative data were collected via an online questionnaire completed by 276 volunteers operating within the UK third sector. Participation was voluntary and anonymous, with recruitment into the study being conducted through sector networks, direct contact with organisations and organisational distribution channels.

The survey included Likert-scale items capturing perceptions of leadership, organisational culture,

talent management, recognition, engagement, training and development, and retention intention. Items were rated on a five-point Likert scale (Likert, 1932), which is widely used for attitudinal measurement and appropriate for composite scale construction (Boone and Boone, 2012). Retention intention was measured as a forward-looking indicator of anticipated continuation in their volunteering role over the next 12 months.

Qualitative data was collected through open-ended questions embedded in the same questionnaire, inviting participants to describe leadership qualities, factors shaping feelings of being valued and supported, and reasons for continuing or exiting previous roles.

Measures and Analysis

Composite scores were calculated for each construct by averaging item responses, preserving the original Likert metric and enabling comparison across constructs (Boone and Boone, 2012). Descriptive statistics and Pearson correlations were used to examine relationships between variables.

Qualitative responses were analysed using reflexive thematic analysis, with coding conducted inductively and themes developed iteratively (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Themes were then mapped explicitly onto quantitative patterns during interpretation, consistent with the explanatory sequential logic of integration (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018).

Limitations

The cross-sectional design limits causal inference, and retention intention may not translate directly into subsequent retention behaviour. All measures were self-reported, creating potential for common method variance. The qualitative dataset comprised short-text responses rather than interviews, limiting depth. These limitations are accounted for in interpreting the findings and claims.

4. Findings

This section presents the empirical findings of the study, organised in line with the three hypotheses underpinning the research. Quantitative results are reported first to establish patterns of association between concepts, followed by qualitative findings used to explain and explain these patterns. Consistent with the explanatory sequential mixed-methods design, emphasis is placed on the relative strength and meaning of relationships rather than on causal inference.

4.1 Descriptive Overview of Key Constructs

Across the sample (N = 276), respondents reported generally positive perceptions of leadership, organisational culture, recognition, engagement, and training and development. Mean scores for most constructs were above the neutral midpoint, indicating broad endorsement of these aspects of the volunteer experience. Engagement recorded one

of the highest composite mean scores (M = 3.87, SD = 0.46), followed closely by recognition (M = 3.81, SD = 0.58) and organisational culture (M = 3.79, SD = 0.56). Leadership (M = 3.62, SD = 0.37) and talent management (M = 3.76, SD = 0.39) were also positively rated, though with lower variability.

Retention intention recorded the highest overall mean (M = 3.93, SD = 0.82), suggesting that, at the point of data collection, most respondents anticipated continuing their involvement in the third sector over the following 12 months. However, this headline figure masks important variation in the factors associated with retention intention, explored in subsequent sections.

Item-level analysis revealed a consistent pattern across constructs: even the lowest-rated items remained above the neutral midpoint, indicating relative rather than absolute dissatisfaction. This suggests that variation in outcomes is shaped less by overt dissatisfaction and more by differential perceptions of feasibility, confidence, and support.

4.2 Hypothesis 1: Leadership, Organisational Culture, and Engagement

Hypothesis 1 proposed that leadership behaviours and organisational culture would be positively associated with volunteer engagement and retention intention. Quantitative analysis partially supported this hypothesis.

Leadership demonstrated the strongest association with engagement of all constructs measured ($r = .40$), indicating a moderate positive relationship. Organisational culture was also positively associated with engagement, though to a lesser extent ($r = .16$). These findings suggest that volunteers who perceive leadership as consistent, inclusive, and values-driven, and who experience a positive organisational culture, are more likely to report higher levels of engagement in their roles.

In contrast, the relationship between leadership and retention intention was weaker ($r = .17$), and organisational culture showed no meaningful association with retention intention ($r = -.04$). Engagement itself was only weakly associated with retention intention ($r = .15$). These results indicate that while leadership and culture play an important role in shaping volunteers' emotional connection and day-to-day experience, their influence on anticipated continuation is limited.

Qualitative responses illuminate this divergence. Volunteers frequently described leadership in relational terms, emphasising visibility, approachability, consistency, and value alignment. Positive leadership was associated with feeling respected, included, and motivated, reinforcing engagement. However, decisions about whether to remain involved were often framed as contingent on practical considerations, such as time availability, role demands, and personal circumstances, rather

than leadership quality alone. Organisational culture was similarly described as shaping how volunteering felt, rather than whether it would continue indefinitely.

These findings suggest that leadership and culture operate primarily at the level of experience quality, fostering engagement without reliably translating into retention intention.

4.3 Hypothesis 2: Talent Management and Recognition

Hypothesis 2 proposed that talent management practices and recognition would be positively associated with both engagement and retention intention. The findings again provide partial support, revealing important distinctions between these constructs.

Talent management demonstrated a moderate positive association with engagement ($r = .38$), second only to leadership in strength. It also showed a small but meaningful association with retention intention ($r = .16$). Item-level analysis indicated that structured induction, clear role descriptions, and consistent communication were widely endorsed and associated with higher engagement. These practices appear to reduce uncertainty and enable volunteers to participate with confidence.

Recognition, by contrast, displayed a markedly different pattern. Recognition recorded one of the highest composite mean scores ($M = 3.81$), and several recognition-related items ranked among the highest-rated in the dataset, including “leaders show appreciation” ($M = 3.98$) and “recognition does not have to be financial to feel meaningful” ($M = 3.94$). Despite this strong endorsement, recognition exhibited only a weak association with engagement ($r = .12$) and virtually no relationship with retention intention ($r = .01$).

Item-level dispersion provides further insight. Recognition items clustered tightly at the upper end of the scale, indicating limited variance. In contrast, the talent management item “I am more likely to stay when I receive feedback on my contribution” recorded a moderate mean ($M = 3.60$) alongside one of the highest standard deviations in the dataset ($SD = 1.04$), suggesting substantial disagreement among respondents.

Qualitative data support this interpretation. Volunteers consistently described appreciation as expected and important, but rarely framed recognition as influencing their decision to stay. Feedback, however, was experienced ambivalently. Some volunteers valued supportive, informal feedback as confidence-building, while others perceived feedback resembling performance appraisal as inappropriate within a voluntary relationship. This polarity helps explain why talent management predicts engagement and retention modestly overall, while recognition functions as a

baseline relational expectation rather than a differentiating retention mechanism.

4.4 Hypothesis 3: Training, Development, and Retention Intention

Hypothesis 3 proposed that engagement and access to training and development opportunities would be positively associated with retention intention. The findings provide the strongest support for this hypothesis, while also challenging assumptions about the role of engagement.

Training and development demonstrated the strongest association with retention intention across all constructs ($r = .20$). Although modest in absolute terms, this relationship was stronger than those observed for leadership, engagement, recognition, or organisational culture. Training and development also recorded a relatively high mean score ($M = 3.79$) with moderate variability ($SD = 0.46$), indicating sufficient dispersion to differentiate retention intention.

Notably, training and development showed very little association with engagement ($r = .07$). This suggests that development does not primarily enhance emotional involvement but instead influences volunteers’ perceived capacity to continue. Item-level analysis reinforces this pattern. Items such as “I am more likely to continue volunteering if I can learn or develop through the role” ($M = 3.76$, $SD = 0.96$) and “training improves my skills and confidence” ($M = 3.71$, $SD = 1.04$) showed both strong endorsement and meaningful variation.

Qualitative responses consistently linked personal development to increased confidence, preparedness, and role sustainability. Volunteers described training and informal learning as helping them feel capable of meeting role demands and managing responsibilities over time which made them feel more confident and secure. Conversely, insufficient guidance or unclear preparation was frequently cited by respondents who had previously stepped back from volunteering. Importantly, training was rarely framed as a reward; rather, it was understood as enabling continued participation.

These findings indicate that training and development operate through a distinct mechanism to leadership, culture, and recognition. Whereas those factors shape engagement, development influences feasibility and perceived sustainability.

4.5 Exit History and Retention Context

A substantial proportion of respondents (64.9%) reported having previously left at least one volunteering role. When asked about reasons for exit, the most frequently cited factors were lack of organisational structure or support and difficult relationships with staff or other volunteers. Insufficient training or induction was cited far less frequently as a direct reason for leaving.

At first glance, this appears to conflict with the stronger association between training and retention intention. However, this pattern suggests that training does not function as a proximate trigger for exit, but rather as a cumulative condition shaping volunteers' confidence and capacity over time. Exit reasons capture immediate catalysts, whereas retention intention reflects anticipatory judgements about feasibility. Together, these findings reinforce the interpretation of training and development as a stabilising, rather than reactive, retention mechanism.

4.6 Summary of Findings

Taken together, the findings demonstrate a consistent pattern across hypotheses. Leadership, organisational culture, and recognition are strongly associated with engagement and widely endorsed, but exert limited influence on retention intention. Talent management supports engagement and modestly contributes to retention by reducing uncertainty and friction. Training and development emerge as the most influential organisational predictor of retention intention, operating through perceived feasibility and role sustainability rather than emotional attachment.

These results highlight a clear distinction between factors that shape how volunteering feels and those that shape whether it can be sustained. The implications of this distinction are explored in the following discussion section.

5. Discussion

This study set out to examine whether organisational factors commonly assumed to drive volunteer retention operate in the ways dominant theories suggest. By empirically disentangling engagement from retention intention, the findings challenge engagement-centric models of volunteer retention and point towards feasibility and role sustainability as critical, yet under-theorised, determinants of continued participation.

5.1 Engagement not as a Retention Mechanism

Across the dataset, leadership behaviours, organisational culture, and recognition were strongly associated with volunteer engagement, confirming a substantial body of prior research demonstrating the importance of relational quality, value alignment, and supportive leadership in shaping positive volunteer experiences (Bass and Riggio, 2006; Dwyer et al., 2013; Vecina et al., 2012). These findings reaffirm that leadership and culture matter greatly for how volunteering feels and for the emotional and psychological rewards volunteers derive from their roles.

However, the weak and inconsistent associations between engagement and retention intention observed in this study echo growing empirical concerns within the literature (Studer and von

Schnurbein, 2013; Warburton et al., 2018). High engagement was widespread across the sample, yet it did not reliably predict intentions to remain involved. This pattern suggests that engagement functions primarily as an indicator of experience quality rather than as a mechanism governing participation duration.

This distinction has important theoretical implications. Engagement theory, particularly as articulated within organisational behaviour research, assumes a context in which exit is constrained by contractual, financial, and institutional factors (Kahn, 1990; Saks, 2006). In volunteering, where participation is discretionary and exit costs are low, the motivational force of engagement is insufficient to override external constraints such as time availability, competing responsibilities, or changes in health and life stage (Hustinx and Lammertyn, 2003; Wilson, 2012). Engagement may therefore be necessary for meaningful participation, but it is not sufficient to sustain it.

5.2 Leadership, Culture, and the Limits of Relational Retention Models

The findings related to Hypothesis 1 further clarify the role of leadership and organisational culture in volunteer contexts. Leadership demonstrated the strongest association with engagement, while organisational culture also contributed positively, albeit more modestly. These results align with Transformational Leadership Theory and organisational culture frameworks that emphasise meaning-making, belonging, and value congruence as central to motivation and commitment (Bass, 1985; Schein, 2010).

Yet, neither leadership nor culture exhibited strong associations with retention intention. This suggests that while relational quality and cultural alignment enhance volunteers' sense of pride, inclusion, and enjoyment, they do not substantially extend the duration of participation in isolation. In other words, leadership and culture shape the quality of engagement but have limited influence over its longevity.

This finding challenges implicit assumptions within both academic and practitioner discourses that improved leadership or culture will necessarily resolve retention problems. It does not diminish the importance of leadership; rather, it reframes its function. Leadership appears to operate as an experiential and relational resource rather than as a retention guarantee. In voluntary settings, leaders may create conditions for meaningful involvement, but they cannot fully offset external constraints or lifecycle dynamics that shape retention decisions.

5.3 Recognition as Baseline Expectation Rather Than Differentiator

The findings related to Hypothesis 2 further complicate social exchange interpretations of volunteer retention. Recognition was among the

most highly endorsed constructs in the study, indicating that volunteers strongly value appreciation and acknowledgment. However, recognition showed virtually no relationship with retention intention and only a weak association with engagement.

This pattern suggests that recognition may function as a baseline relational expectation rather than as a differentiating retention mechanism. Within Social Exchange Theory, continued participation is often framed as a response to perceived reciprocity and organisational support (Blau, 1964; Eisenberger et al., 1986). However, in voluntary contexts, where appreciation is expected and morally normative, its absence may generate dissatisfaction, but its presence does not necessarily bind volunteers into ongoing exchange relationships.

Qualitative findings reinforce this interpretation. Volunteers rarely framed recognition as influencing their decision to remain involved, instead describing it as something that should be present as a matter of respect. This supports prior critiques suggesting that social exchange models may overestimate the binding force of reciprocity in non-contractual contexts, where volunteers retain autonomy to exit without material or reputational loss (Studer and von Schnurbein, 2013).

5.4 Training, Development, and Feasibility as Retention Pathways

The strongest and most theoretically significant finding emerges from Hypothesis 3. Training and development demonstrated the strongest association with retention intention across all constructs, despite exhibiting little relationship with engagement. This pattern indicates that development does not primarily function as a motivational enhancer, but rather as a feasibility mechanism.

Qualitative data provide critical insight into this relationship. Volunteers consistently linked training and development to confidence, preparedness, and perceived capacity to meet role demands. Where volunteers felt underprepared or uncertain, continued participation was framed as increasingly difficult to sustain, even in the presence of positive leadership and strong identification with organisational purpose.

This finding aligns with sociological accounts of volunteering that emphasise capacity, role fit, and lifecycle dynamics over motivational accumulation (Haski-Leventhal and Bargal, 2008; Hustinx et al., 2010). Training and development appear to operate cumulatively, shaping volunteers' anticipatory judgements about whether participation remains viable over time. This helps reconcile the apparent contradiction between exit reasons and retention intention: training may not trigger exit directly, but it stabilises participation by maintaining feasibility.

5.5 Reframing Volunteer Retention as a Feasibility Process

Taken together, the findings support a feasibility-based reframing of volunteer retention. Rather than conceptualising retention as the outcome of ever-increasing engagement, the evidence suggests that retention is conditional and bounded. Engagement shapes experience quality; feasibility shapes sustainability.

This reframing helps explain why high engagement so often coexists with volunteer exit. Volunteers may leave not because they are dissatisfied, but because participation no longer fits within changing life circumstances. Exit, in this sense, may represent a rational and ethical decision rather than organisational failure (Macduff, 2005; Wilson, 2012).

By foregrounding feasibility, this study extends existing theory without rejecting it. Leadership, culture, and recognition remain essential for meaningful participation, but their influence is limited unless organisational conditions support sustained involvement. Retention, therefore, should be understood as the maintenance of feasible participation over time, rather than as the accumulation of motivational states.

6. Conclusion

This study examined volunteer retention in the UK third sector through a mixed-methods perspective, challenging the dominant assumption that engagement naturally leads to sustained participation. By empirically separating engagement from retention intention, the findings demonstrate that while leadership, organisational culture, and recognition strongly shape volunteers' experiences but they exert limited influence over whether volunteering can be sustained.

The central contribution of this article lies in its feasibility-based reframing of volunteer retention. Engagement emerges as a necessary condition for meaningful participation, but not a sufficient condition for longevity. Training and development, by contrast, play a critical role in sustaining retention intention by supporting confidence, preparedness, and role sustainability. Retention is therefore better understood as a conditional process shaped by organisational feasibility and limited by lifecycle constraints, rather than as a simple function of motivational accumulation.

Methodologically, the explanatory sequential mixed-methods design strengthens this contribution by linking statistical patterns to volunteers' own accounts of participation and exit. This integration highlights the importance of examining not only whether volunteers feel engaged, but whether organisational conditions enable continued involvement over time.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. The cross-sectional design restricts causal inference, and retention intention may not translate directly into observed behaviour. The reliance on self-reported data introduces potential common method bias, and the qualitative data lack the depth of interview-based approaches. Future research would benefit from longitudinal designs that track feasibility, engagement, and participation over time, as well as from the development of more explicit measures of feasibility and role sustainability.

For practice, the findings suggest a shift in emphasis. Efforts to improve volunteer retention should move beyond strategies focused solely on recognition and engagement and towards the design of roles that remain feasible across changing life circumstances. This includes investment in training, clear role expectations, flexible participation structures, and ongoing support that sustains volunteers' capacity to contribute.

In conclusion, engagement is not enough. Volunteer retention depends on whether participation remains feasible. Recognising this distinction offers a more realistic, ethical, and theoretically robust foundation for understanding why volunteers stay, why they leave, and what organisations can reasonably do to support sustained involvement over time.

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